

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Morakinyo**FIRST NAME:** Olumide**PROGRAM CODE:** MSDD**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied U.S. conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word on Windows 10

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Academic Writing (EUCLID 2019, 1 - 4)
2. Style Guide (EUCLID 2019, 24-26)
3. Rules of Thumb for Writing Papers (EUCLID 2019, 14 - 16)
4. Abbreviations (EUCLID 2019, 44 - 45)
5. Latin Abbreviations and Expressions (EUCLID 2019, 56 - 61)
6. List of works Cited (EUCLID 2019, 10)
7. When Not to Cite (EUCLID 2019, 9 - 10)

A REVIEW OF ACADEMIC WRITING SKILLS

1) INTRODUCTION

At first, taking a cursory look at the course ACA-401, I wondered what would be the content of a response paper that focused on the appropriate use of English in writing academic and professional documents. Having written two scholarly works during my undergraduate and graduate studies at University, I thought it would be a familiar discourse topic. However, the course has exposed me to the rules and specifics of different origins of the language: the Standard British English (SBE) and the Standard American English (SAE) while highlighting key considerations and points of note for each.

One of the critical outcomes of studying the ACA-401 Period One is to ensure students can present their thesis as objectively as possible and in an unbiased manner. Although many of the grammar rules to be observed in academic writing are basic rules of the English language, the effect of their usage or non-usage is more revealing in an academic paper. Such could result in ambiguity or outright misinterpretation of the idea presented by the writer. This response paper summarizes the learnings from the course material and impacts on my academic writing style.

2)ACADEMIC WRITING

The idea of academic writing being a whole arm of study and having a catalog of rules and regulations was entirely new to me. Formal writing was not emphasized to this extent during my previous study episodes for undergraduate and postgraduate. Going through this course pack offers me a whole new perspective on the subject and highlights the criticality of complying with the rules to write a good essay.

One of the points I find contradictory is achieving balance in my essay (EUCLID 2019, 2). The material advises presenting both sides of an argument when there is an opposing and evidence-based viewpoint. This rule suggests that the author's conclusion will be supported by more definitive evidence to the opposite view and the ability to present evidence in a compelling manner for the target audience. The three parts of an essay were introduced: the introduction, the body, and the conclusion. The point never to present any new information or ideas in the conclusion section is vital.

3)STYLE GUIDE

I found the course pack quite helpful in learning about the formatting and style for this RP. It very evidently showed me how to format a long citation. I was going to do it manually. A combination of video and reading materials to learn about a course, in my experience, is more effective than having only a text to be read. Good knowledge of Microsoft word is required to produce a consistent paper with EUCLID's Chicago writing style (EUCLID 2019, 24).

The style guide serves as a standard to benchmark the writing against. It is similar to the standard reference method used in laboratory analysis, which is universally accepted. Once the method is quoted against a data set, it is taken that the results are valid for the parameter in question. To compare the data set from one laboratory with data set from another laboratory, both must reference the same standard method.

I also find it very enlightening to know that different professions have their preferred writing styles that everyone in the industry is expected to adhere to, to eliminate ambiguity for their various audiences. A freelance writer would have to be very versatile and knowledgeable in writing styles to be able to adapt his writing based on the format that is acceptable to a specific audience per time. I think that it is enough for a freelance writer to master the use of punctuations, which is considered to be universal. However, there may be some flexibility in styles as different standards have different rules, which are still debatable (EUCLID 2019, 24). The course pack clarifies that a creative or freelance writer's work may find ready acceptance by adhering to some of the rules of styles than for a technical or proposal writer who must adhere strictly specified style regulations.

4) RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING PAPERS - TAKE THE VIEWS YOU ARE DISCUSSING SERIOUSLY

Academic papers mostly address current and contemporary issues and present ideas that can be built upon as knowledge evolves. Usually, published works have been peer-reviewed by other professionals in the field being addressed and found the content beneficial to the larger body of knowledge and qualified for publishing. EUCLID (2019, 15) discusses the idea of criticizing one's viewpoint if it contradicts or tries to discredit another author who is considered an authority in the field.

However, the question arises of whether the effects of technological advancements in data collection and improvement in research methodologies, including broader data sets and population samples, could reveal new evidence that could invalidate previous evidence-based studies. I can only conclude that the new research would have a different premise on which the data and evidence is based. It does not invalidate the previous work but only serves to build on existing knowledge in the field. I agree with the course material point that specifies treating "misinterpretation" as the default setting.

I would deduce from this instruction that an author's work cannot be invalidated by new evidence or a unique premise of the study. An example is the various research and ideas that have been developed about the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic. At the outset of the pandemic, how the virus transmits was not well understood, further research efforts resulted in evidence-based conclusions validating different transmission means, leading to more considerations. Julian W Tang in his article on "*interpreting scientific evidence – uncertainty, confusion, and delays*" also discussed the acceptability of the virus transmission through different now-proven means, including airborne transmission by the World Health Organization (Tang 2020, 2).

An editorial in the Lancet Respiratory Medicine further states the following

In July, over 200 scientists published a statement calling for international bodies to recognize the potential for airborne spread of COVID-19 as they were concerned that people would not be fully protected by adhering to the current recommendations. On Oct 5, 2020, the CDC updated their COVID-19 webpage to say that there is growing evidence that COVID-19 infection can occur from airborne exposure to the virus under certain circumstances (Editorial 2020).

However, these new conclusions based on more evidence and more data population did not invalidate earlier assertions that the virus may not have been airborne.

5) ABBREVIATIONS

The instruction about the use of abbreviations was very insightful. It specifies ensuring that the audience does not get confused by numerous abbreviations that they may not be used to (EUCLID 2019, 44). Readers may have to keep referring back to the

definition of acronyms when there are too many of them in a write-up. In the chemical field where I work, abbreviations are used frequently because of the complicated names of many of the chemicals used in analytical procedures (e.g. EDTA for Ethylene diamine tetraacetic acid, NORM for naturally occurring radioactive material). However, such abbreviations are usually acronyms that have become widely accepted in the industry but would require proper definition in a text that is meant for an audience beyond chemical industry experts.

The use of acronyms and abbreviations has been on the increase in more recent years. Pop, Anamaria Mirabella and Sim, Monica Ariana stated in their paper *the use of acronyms and initialisms in business English* "as literacy rose, and as advances in science and technology brought with them more complicated terms and concepts, the practice of abbreviating terms became increasingly convenient. In business, industry, education, and government, acronyms and initialisms are often used by people working within the same fields." (Ariana and Monica 2009, 557) The course pack also emphasizes that "Abbreviations should be used only in contexts where they are clear to readers. . . ." (EUCLID 2019, 44).

I find this to be critical to avoid misinterpretation by the readers because some abbreviations may mean different things to different professions but they are composed of the same letters or combination of letters (e.g., UPS could mean United Parcel Service for a courier worker or Uninterruptable Power Supply in the power industry or User Profile System for an information technology audience. FDA could represent Food and drug administration or functional data analysis for an information technology audience, or front driving axle in automotive engineering). The saying that "the end justifies the means" is entirely appropriate in using abbreviations.

Summarily, abbreviations should be clear and unambiguous in a piece of writing to support the paper's overall goal, which is to present information and ideas in a clear and concise manner that the audience can understand.

6) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

The use of Latin abbreviations is explicitly discouraged in the course pack material except when there is no suitable English equivalent that can appropriately convey the message (EUCLID 2019, 51, 56). The ultimate aim is to avoid confusing the audience and express one's writing in the simplest forms possible. It is interesting to note that the Latin language has significantly influenced the English language and other languages over the years and has come to stay in some English language expressions. The University of Nebraska, in its article on *Latin Terms Used in Writing*, states that "Latin words and expressions are present in virtually all languages around the world, as well as in different scientific and academic fields" (Nebraska 2021).

It came as a refresher to me seeing those everyday English language words and to link them back to their Latin roots, and also elucidate their proper usage in the English language. As much as the student is admonished to avoid the use of confusing abbreviations, I think that some of the ubiquitous ones (such as e.g., i.e.) would not confuse any audience because they must have learned the use of these abbreviations right from elementary English. I

would use "e.g., e.t.c., i.e., et al.," in my writing when they convey my message best but will still pay attention to limit their use overall.

7) LIST OF WORKS CITED

A very critical aspect of academic writing is the citation, which ensures that all the works that were consulted in the process of writing a paper have been credited with the information sourced from them. Citation is ultimately meant to avoid plagiarism. I was curious to research more on when to use the list of references or bibliography in academic writing.

In writing a paper, the writer is expected to conduct literature review to base his thesis on prior body of knowledge which involves referring to studies undertaken by other researchers in the field. All the works cited in a writing are expected to be listed out at the end of the paper to help the reader track and verify the citations in the article. This list could either be a list of references or a bibliography. This citation is similar to what obtains in my work as a Laboratory technologist; we are required to quote a standard method to which each analysis is to be referenced against. As Nigeria, the country where I work, does not have its standard method list, we always reference the American Society of Testing and Materials (ASTM) standard method, which is globally accepted. Anyone looking at the analytical data can relate to these ASTM methods. I suppose the list of references or bibliographies plays a similar role in academic paper writing.

On its website, the editors of Encyclopedia Britannica state, "the primary purpose of descriptive bibliography is to organize detailed information culled from a mass of materials in a systematic way so that others can have access to useful information." (Britannica n.d.). A bibliography is usually more elaborate and comprehensive than a list of references. It is expected to contain a list of all the consulted works, not necessarily only those cited in the writing. Consistency is the key in any academic writing and the best way to avoid confusing the readers (EUCLID 2019, 51).

8) WHEN NOT TO CITE

I find this heading in the ACA 401 course pack very surprising, and I would not have thought a section of the course pack would be devoted to helping the student understand when he does not have to reference the source of information. However, it became apparent that as much as we want to give credit to the author of data used in our writing, there must be other contents of the write-up that would not be attributed to an author without being deemed as plagiarism. This does not imply that the information not cited is credited to the person writing the paper, but it means that such information is public knowledge (EUCLID 2019, 10).

I have come across papers and academic presentations where more than half of the whole writing is cited. I find such writing boring and not having the expected flow to

captivate a reader to continue reading to the paper's end. The question however arises of how to determine whether to cite or not.

To determine whether a piece of information is public knowledge or not, I believe there should be a measurable standard to benchmark against. The checklist in the course pack that defines when not to cite seems to me to be subjective and readily amenable to the author's bias and perspective. Students' background and widely varied knowledge base readily influence what each person would consider as public knowledge. I reason that public knowledge information should be described and defined in more tangible ways as advocated by Amy England in her work, "The Dynamic Nature of Common Knowledge." (Amy 2008, 104 - 113). This could be due to my inclination due to my work in a field where everything must have tangible and measurable value.

9) CONCLUSION

The ACA-401 International Academic and Professional Paper Writing course encompasses aspects of writing that may seem inconsequential but on deep examination would be critical to presenting a standard academic work. Every student should take a class on academic writing pedagogy at some point in their program as it is a foundation to build upon in other writing and study. Studying the course is both rewarding and satisfactory.

Citation of referenced works to avoid plagiarism is a part of it where I need to devote more effort and ensure consistency is maintained. Knowing when not to cite requires a balance of objectivity and some personal bias that could emanate from previous exposures or learnings. Going forward in my studies, I will pay particular attention to the writing style of academic papers that I read, whether for review or reference. I will observe the writing style used in developing the work, the abbreviations used, the citation style, and all the other details that make up academic writing. These will also be strictly adhered to in writing my papers as I progress in my studies.

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